

Elimination of organophosphate pesticides from vegetables using chemical neutralizer: pesticides denatured from *Solanum melongena* L. (Brinjal) Using BTMAC.

Anuj Thapar^{1*}, Aman Zalawadia², Omkar V. Pokharkar³, Sahil S. Satam⁴

¹⁻⁴ D.Y. Patil University, School of Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, C.B.D
Belapur – 400614, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

*Email: Anujthapar29@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

Organophosphate or phosphate ester is the general name for esters of phosphoric acid. Many of the most important biochemicals are organophosphates, including DNA and RNA as well as many cofactors that are essential for life. Organophosphates are the basis of many insecticides, herbicides, and nerve agents. The United States Environmental Protection Agency lists organophosphates as very highly acutely toxic to bees, wildlife, and humans. Recent studies suggest a possible link to adverse effects in the neurobehavioral development of fetuses and children, even at very low levels of exposure. Organophosphates are widely used as solvents, plasticizers, and EP additives. These pesticides are not removed from vegetables by the conventional method of washing so there is need to find some alternative. So to neutralize these pesticides, a chemical neutralizer benzyltrimethyl ammonium chloride was used by applying a suitable method. The main objective of this chemical neutralizer is to eliminate the organophosphate pesticides from vegetables. Three pesticides namely chlorpyrifos, dimethoate and Malathion was applied on vegetables-brinjal. The method includes the application of chemical neutralizer. The Chemical neutralizer helps in denaturation of organophosphate pesticide. Chemical neutralizer containing benzyltrimethyl ammonium chloride about 50% by weight means 50 gram of the benzyltrimethyl ammonium chloride of chemical dissolved in 100 milliliters of solvent or distilled water. Different concentrations of benzyltrimethyl ammonium chloride were also used for neutralization, but 50% concentration was best and didn't affect the vegetables. After pesticide application, the brinjals were dipped in chemical neutralizer for about an hour to neutralize the pesticide, then the samples underwent distilled water wash to remove neutralizer contents, these brinjals were tested for GCMS (Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry). The results were very effective. The contents of pesticide were neutralized up to 70% in contrast with that of the contents of only pesticides. This solution is a noncorrosive, nontoxic, nonflammable decontaminant, which can be used to neutralize organophosphate pesticides from vegetables. This chemical is useful on all vegetables containing organophosphorus pesticide.

KEYWORDS: Pesticides, vegetables, BTMAC, Organophosphate, Malathion, Dimethoate, Chlorpyrifos.

INTRODUCTION

Pesticides are chemical substances used to kill insects and animals that destroy crops. They are

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characterized by pronounced persistence against chemical/biological degradation, high environmental mobility, strong tendency for bioaccumulation in human and animal tissues, and significant impacts on human health and the environment, even at extremely low concentrations (H. Liu et al., 2009). India is a predominantly agrarian country with about 60-80% rural population. Pesticides are routinely used for advanced farming. These are readily available over the counter. Therefore, a pesticide is an easy access source for suicidal purpose particularly after trivial family squabbles. Such little petty quarrels often that result in consumption of

pesticide for suicide purpose is a matter of routine news in local dailies. Poisoning is seldom included as a priority for health research in India, though every year, hundreds of people are losing their lives prematurely from pesticide poisoning (HS Bawasker et al., 2005). Classification of pesticides is as per their acute toxicity, as classified by the World Health Organization. This classification includes Class Ia – Extremely hazardous, demarcated in red; Class Ib – Highly Hazardous, symbolized by a yellow triangle; Class II – Moderately Hazardous, marked by a blue triangle. Class III is known as “Slightly Hazardous” while the remaining class is supposed to be “Not likely to be Hazardous”. It is to be noted here that two-thirds of the pesticides consumed here fall under WHO Class I and II pesticides. From 1998 to 2005, the decline in Class Ia pesticides has been only 2% - from 11% to 9% (K Kuruganti et al., 2007).

Figure 1. Depicts the different toxicity levels of pesticides

Material and Methods

Following Organophosphate Pesticides were employed:

1. Chlorpyrifos 20% EC
2. Malathion 50% EC
3. Dimethoate 30% EC

The above mentioned pesticides were purchased from Namdeo Umaji Agritech (India) Pvt. Ltd, Byculla.

Following compound was used:

Benzyltrimethyl Ammonium Chloride pure (BTMAC). This compound was purchased from SRL.

Figure 2. Depicts the structure of BTMAC

Vegetable used for the study: Brinjal (*Solanum melongena*)

110%Solution Preparation:

The compound BTMAC was taken as a pure form then 11gm was weighed on the weighing machine and 10ml of distilled water was taken in the beaker.

To the 10ml distilled water, 11gm of BTMAC was added and was mixed by shaking gently.

Treatment of BTMAC solution 110% concentration on Brinjal:

Fresh brinjal was taken from the market and were kept in a container. To the brinjal, BTMAC – 110% concentrated solution was sprayed with the help of sprayer. The brinjals were under observation.

BTMAC 50%Solution Preparation:

The compound BTMAC was taken as a pure form and 5gm was weighed on the weighing machine. Then 10ml of distilled water was taken in the beaker. To the 10ml distilled water, 5gm of BTMAC was added and was mixed by shaking gently (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Treatment of BTEAC solution 50% concentration on Brinjal:

Fresh brinjals were purchased from the market and were kept in a container. To the brinjals, BTMAC – 50% concentrated solution was sprayed with the help of sprayer. The brinjals were kept for observation.

Sample Preparation for GCMS:

Three organophosphorus pesticide namely chlorpyrifos, dimethoate and Malathion were taken. Then the brinjals were sprayed with these pesticides one by one. The brinjal were dried before spraying with each of the pesticides. After the pesticide application, the brinjals were again air dried. After air drying, the brinjals were dipped in BTMAC 50% concentration and few of them dipped in distilled water which was taken as a blank (**Figure-5**). The brinjals were kept for about an hour in BTMAC 50% concentration and distilled water. After one hour, the brinjals were removed and they were allowed to air dry again. The brinjals removed from BTMAC 50% concentration was washed with distilled water. These brinjals after drying were given for GCMS for detection of pesticide residue (**Figure-3**) The GCMS was performed at Microchem Silliker, Mahape, Navi Mumbai (**Figure 11,Figure 12,Figure 13,Figure 14**).

Preparation of the samples of brinjal for GCMS testing:

Sample 1 (Control sample) was prepared by spraying Pesticides on brinjals and then the brinjals were dipped into the distilled water.

Sample 2 (Test sample) was prepared by Pesticides were sprayed on brinjal and then the brinjals were dipped into the chemical neutralizer BTMAC 50% which was prepared (50g in 100ml of distilled water) and then the brinjals were washed with distilled water.

Figure 3. Depicts the step by step procedure.

Figure-4. (Left) beaker containing distilled water (control) and (right) beaker containing BTMAC 50% (test).

Figure 5. (Left) Brinjals dipped in distilled water (control) and (right) brinjals dipped in the BTMAC 50% solution (test).

Results

The effect of BTMAC 110% concentration on brinjals:

The Brinjal was tested with different concentrations of pesticides and chemical neutralizer on it. The neutralizer (BTMAC) was made with 110% concentration and sprayed on brinjal.

Figure 4. On day 4, Brinjal was damaged due to high concentration of BTMAC (110%).

Control was also made on which nothing was sprayed. This was Day-1. Chemical neutralizer BTMAC 110% concentration (11g in 10ml distilled water) was sprayed on brinjal.

Figure 5. Brinjal sample 2 (in the middle) showed abnormal secretion around it on day 1.

Figure 6. Brinjal samples 1 and 3 remained normal whereas sample 2 continued to show abnormality on day 2

Figure 7. Sample 1 and 2 were on the verge of rotting but sample 3 treated with BTMAC and distilled water remained normal on day 3 and 4.

Effect of BTMAC 50% concentration on brinjal:

Three samples of brinjals were prepared.

- Sample 1 – Control
- Sample 2 – 50% chemical neutralizer BTMAC (i.e. 50g in 100ml distilled water) was sprayed on brinjal.
- Sample 3 - 50% chemical neutralizer BTMAC (i.e. 50g in 100ml distilled water) was sprayed on brinjal and then washed with distilled water.

Effect of Organophosphates on brinjal:

Three different types of pesticides were sprayed on the brinjals and were kept for observation. Even after 5 days they appeared normal.

Figure 8. Brinjals sprayed with pesticides under observation.

Results of GCMS:

Results of GCMS performed at Microchem Silliker, Mahape, Navi Mumbai.

Description of the Graph and the table:

Without neutralizer the contents of the different pesticides are Chlorpyrifos 0.080mg/kg, Dimethoate 0.272mg/kg, Omethoate 0.020mg/kg, and Malathion

0.163mg/kg. After using Pesticides these contents become Chlorpyrifos 0.070mg/kg, Dimethoate 0.300mg/kg, Omethoate 0.014mg/kg, and Malathion 0.050mg/kg. The OPs are denatured and neutralized with chemical neutralizer BTMAC solution. In these experiments, Malathion which has class II toxicity level also gets neutralized up to 70 % which is highly effective and is a great result. The chlorpyrifos which has class II toxicity level gets neutralized up to 12.5% which is a very effective (Table-1) and (Graph-1). The Omethoate which was not applied but was detected in the results of GC-MS. Omethoate is also an OP pesticide which has class Ib, Highly Hazardous toxicity level. Omethoate might be applied by the farmer which also gets neutralized up to 30%. These all results are very effective and helps in neutralization of all the Ops. Dimethoate has class II toxicity level (Figure-1). The increased concentration of dimethoate represents that neutralizer wash is not efficient for dimethoate but the cause for increase in concentration has to be studied by initial concentration of dimethoate without water wash. We can conclude that concentration needs to be studied with respect to initial concentration before any wash. The study is only dealing with comparing of water wash and neutralizer washes which will not explain the cause of increased level of dimethoate.

Effect of BTMAC 110% concentration on brinjal:

As per the treatment of BTMAC 110% concentration on brinjal described in the methods section, the brinjals were normal on day 1, but on day 4, the control was damaged whereas the brinjals on which BTMAC 110% were also damaged. Henceforth, it was concluded from the result that, the brinjals were not able to bear high concentration of BTMAC solution on it. The result is quite evident in the above given (Figure 4).

Figure 11. Scanned Test results obtained for the brinjals with pesticide and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 1 (report no. 151605168).

TEST REPORT			
REPORT NO.: 151605168		REPORT DATE : 27/04/2015	
Customer Name	Anuj Thapar		
Address	804, Marathon Galaxy II, LBS Marg, Mulund(W), Mumbai, Maharashtra-400080		
Contact Person	Mr. Anuj Thapar		
Sample(s) Drawn by The Laboratory	No		
Date of Sample Received	21/04/2015		
Date of Starting Analysis	23/04/2015		
Date of Completion	24/04/2015		
Sample Description	Brinjal		
Sample Details	Nature: Solid, Qty: 5No.s, Stamped/Sealed: No, Packing: Plastic Box		
PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Acephate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorfenvinphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos	0.080	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dimethoate	0.272	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Diazinon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dichlorvos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Ethion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Etrimphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenitrothion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Iprobenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Malathion	0.163	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Methamidophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Monocrotophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Omethoate	0.020	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Oxydemeton-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosphamidon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Ethyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosalone	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phorate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Profenophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Quinolphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
4-Bromo-2-Chlorophenol	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Triazophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Edifenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenthion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

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MicroChem Silliker Pvt. Ltd.
MicroChem House,
A-513, TTC Industrial Area, MIDC,
Mahape, Navi Mumbai 400 701, India
Tel. : +91-22-39469700 (Hunting Lines)
Fax : +91-22-39469701
email : customercare@microchem.co.in

www.microchem.co.in

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Figure 12. Scanned Test results obtained for the brinjals with pesticide and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 2 (report no. 151605168).

TEST REPORT			
REPORT NO.: 151605168		REPORT DATE: 27/04/2015	
PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Glufosinate-Ammonium	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Glyphosphate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phenthoate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Pirimiphos-methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Propetamphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Temephos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Thiometon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

Remark : BLQ : Below Limit of Quantification, Quantification Limit : 0.01 mg/kg

..... END

[Signature]
Authorized Signatory

Note: 1. Test results relate to the submitted sample(s) only. 2. Test report shall not be reproduced except in full, without written approval of the laboratory. 3. Laboratory is not responsible for the authenticity of photocopied test report. 4. The test items will not be retained for perishable products and 1 month in the case of non-perishable samples unless otherwise agreed with the customer or as required by the applicable regulation. 5. The tests marked with (*) are not accredited by NABL.

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MicroChem Silliker Pvt. Ltd.
MicroChem House,
A-513, TTC Industrial Area, MIDC,
Mahape, Navi Mumbai 400 701, India
Tel. : +91-22-39469700 (Hunting Lines)
Fax : +91-22-39469701
email : customercare@microchem.co.in

www.microchem.co.in

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Figure 13. Scanned Test results obtained for brinjals with pesticide, neutralizer wash and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 1 (report no. 151605169).

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a Mérieux NutriSciences Company

TEST REPORT			
REPORT NO.: 151605169		REPORT DATE: 27/04/2015	
Customer Name	Anuj Thapar		
Address	804, Marathon Galaxy II, LBS Marg, Mulund(W), Mumbai, Maharashtra-400080		
Contact Person	Mr. Anuj Thapar		
Sample(s) Drawn by The Laboratory	No		
Date of Sample Received	21/04/2015		
Date of Starting Analysis	22/04/2015		
Date of Completion	24/04/2015		
Sample Description	Brinjal		
Sample Details	Nature: Solid, Qty: 5No.s, Stamped/Sealed: No, Packing: Plastic Container		

PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Acephate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorfenvinphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos	0.070	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Chlorpyrifos methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dimethoate	0.300	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Diazinon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Dichlorvos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Ethion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Etrimphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenitrothion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Iprobenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Malathion	0.050	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Methamidophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Monocrotophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Omethoate	0.014	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Oxydemeton-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosphamidon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Ethyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phosalone	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phorate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Profenophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Quinolphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
4-Bromo-2-Chlorophenol	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Triazophos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Edifenphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Fenthion	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

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MicroChem Silliker Pvt. Ltd.
MicroChem House,
A-513, TTC Industrial Area, MIDC,
Mahape, Navi Mumbai 400 701, India
Tel. : +91-22-39469700 (Hunting Lines)
Fax : +91-22-39469701
email : customercare@microchem.co.in

www.microchem.co.in

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Figure 14. Scanned Test results obtained for brinjals with pesticide, neutralizer wash and distilled water wash, Microchem Silliker, page 2 (report no. 151605169).

TEST REPORT			
REPORT NO.: 151605169		REPORT DATE: 27/04/2015	
PARAMETER NAME	RESULT	UOM	METHOD
Glufosinate-Ammonium	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Glyphosphate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Phenthoate	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Pirimiphos-methyl	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Propetamphos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Temephos	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34
Thiometon	BLQ	mg/kg	MC/SOP/INS/34

Remark : BLQ : Below Limit of Quantification, Quantification Limit : 0.01 mg/kg

..... **END**

Authorized Signatory

Note: 1. Test results relate to the submitted sample(s) only. 2. Test report shall not be reproduced except in full, without written approval of the laboratory. 3. Laboratory is not responsible for the authenticity of photocopied test report. 4. The test items will not be retained for perishable products and 1 months in the case of non-perishable samples unless otherwise agreed with the customer or as required by the applicable regulation. 5. The tests marked with (*) are not accredited by NABL.

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MicroChem Silliker Pvt. Ltd.
MicroChem House,
A-513, TTC Industrial Area, MIDC,
Mahape, Navi Mumbai 400 701, India
Tel. : +91-22-39469700 (Hunting Lines)
Fax : +91-22-39469701
email : customercare@microchem.co.in

www.microchem.co.in

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Table 1. Indicates presence of different types of pesticides in brinjal samples with and without chemical neutralizers.

Test for Brinjal		
Name of the Pesticides	Without neutralizers contents of the Pesticides (mg/kg)	With neutralizers contents of the Pesticides (mg/kg)
Chlorpyrifos	0.080	0.070
Dimethoate	0.272	0.300
Malathion	0.163	0.050
Omethoate	0.020	0.014

Effect of BTMAC solution 50% concentration on brinjal:

As per the treatment of BTMAC solution 50% concentration on brinjal described in the methods section, the sample 1 and sample 3 were normal whereas sample 2 had abnormal secretion as shown (Figure 5). Till day 3, there were abnormal secretions in sample 2 and somewhat got rotten whereas there were no changes in sample 1 and sample 3 (Figure-8). On day 4, sample 2 had abnormal secretion and somewhat got rotten and sample 1 somewhat got rotten whereas no changes were observed on sample 3 as shown (Figure-9). Sample 1 was control and sample 3 was treated with BTMAC solution 50% concentration and after treatment it was washed with

Graph 1. Graphical representation of the results obtained from the GCMS test for Brinjals..

PETANT DETAILS:

PATENT OFFICE
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY BUILDING
 S.M. Road, Antop Hill, Mumbai-400 037
 Te No. (091)(022) 24137701, 24141026 FAX No. 02 24130387
 E-mail : mumbai-patent@nic.in
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GOVERNMENT OF INDIA
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 Date/Time : 27/05/2015 12:05:03
 Agent Number:

Docket NO : 11565
 To
 DIPAK SAYAJI KOKANE
 B/703, PRATIK CORNER, PLOT NO.- 49, SEC NO-8/A, AIROLI, NAVI MUMBAI-400708, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA.

Sr. No.	CBR Number	Reference Number /Application Type	Application Number	Title/Remarks	Amount Paid	Amount Computed
1	8214	ORDINARY APPLICATION Pages:-9 , Claims:-0	2058/MUM/2015	CHEMICAL NEUTRALIZER FOR DENATURATION OF PESTICIDES	1760	1760
2		E-101/21388/2015-MUM	2058/MUM/2015	Correspondence	0	0
3		E-2/1286/2015-MUM	2058/MUM/2015	Form2	0	0
Total Amount					1760	1760

Received a sum of Rs. 1760 (Rupees One Thousand Seven Hundred & Sixty only) as under

Payment Mode	Bank Name	Cheque/Draft Number	Cheque/Draft Date	Amount in Rs
Cash	---	---	---	1760

distilled water to remove the chemical neutralizer BTMAC solution 50% concentration.

Effect of Water Wash:

After the treatment of pesticide and chemical neutralizer on brinjal, the brinjal are dried and then washed with distilled water to remove or wash away the chemical neutralizer present on the vegetables. These wash removes all contents of the chemical neutralizer BTMAC solution and therefore there is no other effects on brinjal-vegetables and are good for consumption.

Discussions

The benefits of pesticides include increased food production, increased profits for farmers and the prevention of diseases. Although pests consume or harm a large portion of agricultural crops, without the use of pesticides, it is likely that they would consume a higher percentage. The Registration Committee (RC) registers pesticides for their usage, their MRL in food and commodities are prescribed by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare under PFA (Act), 1954 and rules framed thereunder. What is alarming to note is that in India, MRL as a concept is being wrongly formulated while implementation status is worse. While pesticides are registered without MRLs being necessarily fixed before or during registration, there are no enforcement mechanisms available to ensure liability for violation of MRLs at least by the organized food industry. During evidence to the Joint Parliamentary Committee formed in 2004, representative of the Ministry of Agriculture and the Director General of Health Services admitted that out of 181 pesticides registered at that time, tolerance limits (MRLs) have been fixed for only 71 pesticides. For another 50 pesticides, such tolerance limits were in the process of finalization. It has been concluded that there are about 27 pesticides registered in the country which do not require fixation of tolerance limits. This means 32 pesticides which are still left for tolerance limits to be fixed – for eight of these, it was decided to follow Codex norms for the time being since data was not available and was being collected. Data for 24 pesticides where are “deemed-to-be-registered” has been submitted. As part of this study, an interesting exercise was taken up, to compare the data between registration recommendation for each pesticide and the recommendations of agriculture departments and finally, the recommendations by the company's manufacturing and selling the pesticides. For example, Acephate is registered for use only on Cotton and Safflower in the country. It is not registered for use on Chillies, Brinjal, Cabbage, Cauliflower, Apple, Castor, Mango, Tomato, Potato, Grapes, Okra, Onion, Mustard, Paddy and many other crops where it is being used extensively now. Further, it is also being recommended by the NARS

for use in other crops even without registration! Acephate is being recommended for the control of sap sucking pests in most crops. Further, MRLs have been set only for safflower seed and cotton seed for this pesticide. Survey report conducted by Indian agricultural research institute indicates that a total of 4239 vegetable samples of brinjal, okra, tomato, cabbage, capsicum and cauliflower, collected from various wholesale/retail markets located at different parts of the country were analysed during April 2009-March 2010 by 17 participating laboratories. The pesticide residues were detected in 417 samples out of which 137 samples were found to contain residues of more than one pesticide. Residues detected in most of the samples were below the MRL. In 84 samples the residues were found above MRL levels. The maximum number of detectable samples have been reported by P.C.Cell, New Delhi (225 Samples) followed by IITR, Lucknow (69 samples); PAU, Ludhiana (35 samples); IHR, Bangalore (30 samples) and AAU nAnand (29 samples) laboratories. The pesticides mainly reported by P.C.Cell are chlorpyrifos (59 samples) and endosulfan (69 samples). The most predominantly detected pesticides in vegetable sample by different centres are chlorpyrifos (122 samples), endosulfan (110 samples), profenophos (55 samples) and triazophos (41 samples). Of the various vegetable samples analyzed, highest numbers of pesticides were detected in Okra (184 samples) out of which 11 samples contained residues of chlorpyrifos, cypermetgrin and monocrotophos above MRL. The second highest number of detectable residues were found in tomato samples (110 samples) viz., cauliflower, brinjal and cabbage showed the presence of pesticide residues in 56, 90 and 40 samples, respectively (Aman Zalawadia et al., 2015).

Conclusion

The presence of pesticide residues is a concern for consumers because organophosphates are known to have potential harmful effects to other non-targeted organisms than pests and diseases. People have environmental exposures to pesticides mainly through diet. Human intake due to pesticide residues in food commodities is usually much higher than those related to water consumption and air. The evaluation of pesticide residues in food is nowadays a priority objective to ensure food quality and to protect consumers against possible health risks. Fruits and vegetables are important components of the human diet since they provide essential nutrients that are required for most of the reactions occurring in the body (Anuj Thapar et al., 2015). A high intake of fruits and vegetables (five or more servings per day) has been encouraged not only to prevent consequences due to vitamin deficiency but also to reduce the incidence of major diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases and obesity.

Contamination of fruits and vegetables may result from treatment as well as from conditions such as improper or overuse of pesticides, residues from preceding treatments in the soil and cross contamination (particularly during harvesting). Due to their high solubility in water, organophosphates are distributed in aqueous food such as fruits and related derivatives. These can be dangerous if consumed. In this study, Efforts were made to eliminate the pesticides that were sprayed on the brinjals. The results were breathtaking. The contents of pesticide were neutralized up to 70% in contrast with that of the contents of only pesticides. The solution which was prepared is noncorrosive, nontoxic, nonflammable decontaminant, which can be used to neutralize organophosphate pesticides from vegetables. This chemical is effective on all vegetables containing organophosphorus pesticides.

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Conflict of Interests:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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